

Synthesis in the Pyridine Series.

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It has been recently shown (Basu, *Annalen*, 1934, 512, 131; 1934, 514, 292) that the condensation of different 2-hydroxymethylene cyclohexanones with tautomeric compounds of the ketimine-enamine type, $\text{H N:CR} \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{X} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{N} \cdot \text{CR} : \text{CH} \cdot \text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{CO} \cdot \text{R}$, CO_2R , etc.), gives rise to various *Bz*-tetrahydroquinolines. Substituting the cyclic ketone derivatives by hydroxymethylene compounds (I) derived from open-chain ketones, it would be possible to effect syntheses of numerous pyridine derivatives (II) having a negative substituent at the β -position (*cf.* Späth, *Monatsch*, 1928, 49, 266) thus:

Accordingly, hydroxymethylene compounds obtained from ethyl-phenylketone, *p*-methylacetophenone and methylethylketone were treated with ethyl β -aminocrotonate, when from the reaction products ethyl 2:5-dimethyl-6-phenyl-, 2-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl- and 2:5:6-trimethyl-pyridine-3-carboxylates were respectively obtained. All these pyridine- β -carboxylates are basic substances easily soluble in dilute acids and form additive compounds with picric acid. They are insoluble in water but readily dissolve in ether, alcohol and other common organic solvents. On hydrolysis with caustic potash solution they give the corresponding pyridine- β -carboxylic acids, which are easily soluble in water, alcohol and chloroform, difficultly in ether and acetone and sparingly in petroleum ether. They exhibit the character of amino acids and impart no colouration to ferrous sulphate solution.

In the light of these observations, it appeared probable that by using an enamine compound of the type $R'\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}:\text{CRNH}_2$, a method for the synthesis of β -pyridyl alkyl or aryl ketones might be found. A preliminary condensation in this direction has been brought about between benzoylacetoneamine, $\text{PhCO}\cdot\text{CH}:\text{CMeNH}_2$ and hydroxymethylene *p*-methylacetophenone. From the experimental results so far obtained there are reasons to believe that the product of reaction is 2-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-3-benzoylpyridine [II, $R = \text{Me}$, $R' = (p) \text{Me}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ and $X = \text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$].

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydroxymethylene ethylphenylketone and ethyl β -aminocrotonate: Formation of ethyl 2:5-dimethyl-6-phenylpyridine-3-carboxylate.—15 G. of the hydroxymethylene ketone, prepared according to the method of Claisen and Meyerowitz (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 3275), m.p. 118-19° on crystallisation from alcohol, was dissolved in ether and mixed with ethyl β -aminocrotonate (12 g.). The solution was then heated under reflux on a water-bath for about 15 hours. The ether was driven off and the residual mass was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid when a resinous mass separated out. This was filtered off and the clear acid filtrate was neutralised with sodium carbonate. The oil separating, was extracted with ether, ethereal solution dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether evaporated off. The remaining liquid on distillation at 170-185°/8mm. yielded a solid (12 g.) which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 59°. (Found: N, 5.56. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

Picrate.—The pyridine carboxylate derivative on treatment with an alcoholic solution of picric acid yielded a picrate which on crystallisation from alcohol was obtained in yellow rectangular prisms, m.p. 146°. [Found: N, 11.73. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2(\text{NO}_2)_3\text{OH}$ requires N, 11.57 per cent].

Hydrolysis: Formation of 2:5-dimethyl-6-phenylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid.—The above pyridine carboxylate (6 g.) was refluxed with 24 c.c. of caustic potash solution (15%) till a clear solution was obtained. This was then acidified with hydrochloric acid (to Congo paper) and evaporated to dryness on a boiling water-bath. The whole mass was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution was then concentrated (after charcoaling) and diluted with petroleum ether

when the carboxylic acid was precipitated out. This was collected and crystallised from a mixture (1:1) of the above two solvents in shining flakes, m.p. 140° (decomp.) (Found: N, 5·85. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6·17 per cent).

Hydroxymethylene p-methyl-1-acetophenone and ethyl β-aminocrotonate: Formation of ethyl 2-methyl-6-p-tolylpyridine-3-carboxylate.—The hydroxymethylene derivative of *p*-methylacetophenone was prepared according to Benary, Meyer and Charisius (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 108) and preserved as its sodium salt. The oxymethylene compound was freshly liberated from the above salt before use. Thus 18 g. of the sodium salt were decomposed with dilute acetic acid and the liberated oxymethylene compound was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was then heated with ethyl β-aminocrotonate (12 g.) for about 15 hours. The ether was then evaporated off and the reacted mixture was treated as in the previous case, when the hydrochloric acid solution on neutralisation gave a solid product. This on crystallisation from dilute alcohol was obtained in fine scales, m.p. 54°. (Found: N, 5·60. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 5·49 per cent).

The *picrate* of the above pyridine derivative was prepared as usual and found to crystallise out from alcohol, m.p. 133°. [Found: N, 11·55. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2N$, $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$ requires N, 11·57 per cent].

Hydrolysis: Formation of 2-methyl-6-p-tolylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid.—This was prepared by heating the ester (3 g.) with 12 c.c. of caustic potash solution till a clear solution was obtained. The solution was made acid to Congo paper and evaporated to dryness. Extracting the mass with absolute alcohol and then concentrating the alcoholic solution, the carboxylic acid crystallised out in shining tiny crystals, m.p. 207·8° with decomposition. (Found: N, 6·04. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6·17 per cent).

Hydroxymethylene butanone (Me·CO·CMe·CHOH) and ethyl β-aminocrotonate: Formation of ethyl 2:5:6-trimethylpyridine-3-carboxylate.—12 G. of the hydroxymethylene ketone, obtained from methylethylketone according to the method described by Benary, Meyer and Charisius (*loc. cit.*; cf. Benary, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 600), and ethyl β-aminocrotonate (15 g.) were mixed together and the mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for more than 6 hours. The reaction product on subsequent treatment as usual yielded an oil (9 g.), b.p. 134·36°/11 mm. (Found: N, 7·52. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 7·25 per cent).

This pyridine carboxylate derivative is a yellow refracting liquid, $n_{D20} = 1.5056$. It distills at $256-57^{\circ}/755$ mm. It is insoluble in water but dissolves readily in common organic solvents.

The *picrate*, on crystallisation from alcohol, melts at 157° . [Found: N, 13.39. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N$, $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$ requires N, 13.27 per cent].

A salt was also prepared by adding the pyridine carboxylate to an alcoholic solution of mercuric chloride. It crystallised from alcohol diluted with a few drops of water as fine needles, m.p. 118.5° . The salt is being regarded as $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N$, $HgCl_2$.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 2:5:6-trimethylpyridine—3-carboxylic acid.—The acid was prepared as usual by hydrolysing the ester with caustic potash solution. It was obtained in shining needles from alcohol, m.p. $217-18^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.07. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 8.48 per cent).

Hydroxymethylene p-methylacetophenone and benzoylacetone-amine.—About 4 g. of the former substance were heated with a molecular proportion of benzoylacetone-amine in alcoholic solution. On adding dilute hydrochloric acid to the reaction mixture benzoylacetone was found to separate out. The acid filtrate, however, on neutralisation with sodium carbonate afforded a thick oil which readily gave a *picrate* with an alcoholic solution of picric acid. This on crystallisation from alcohol was obtained in bright yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 191° . The percentage of nitrogen present in the compound was found to be 10.31. The *picrate* [$C_{20}H_{17}ON$, $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$] of 2-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-3-benzoylpyridine, the expected product of reaction between hydroxymethylene *p*-methylacetophenone and benzoylacetone-amine, requires N, 10.85 per cent.

Further work in this direction is in progress. In conclusion, the author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Prof. H. K. Sen for placing the resources of his laboratory at his disposal.